

Pinagpala Publishing Services

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842

ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

VOL.V ISSUE XI

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT

MULTIDISCIPLINARY E-PUBLICATION

November 2025
Monthly Issue
International

Pinagpala
PUBLISHING SERVICES

NBDB Reg. No. 3269
DTI Business Reg. No. 3034433
TIN 293-150-678/ Business Permit No. 8183
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World Education Connect Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume V, Issue XI (November 2025), pp.51-62, International
ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X
Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com
Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services
DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183
National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

PASSING OR LEARNING? UNDERSTANDING THE CORRELATION BETWEEN HIGH SCHOOL PROMOTION PRACTICES AND STUDENTS' MATHEMATICAL PROFICIENCY

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the relationship between mass promotion, where students advance without mastery, and mathematical proficiency among high school learners in Abuyog, Leyte. Twenty-five math teachers participated using a quantitative correlational design and Likert-scale questionnaire. Descriptive statistics and ANOVA analyzed perceptions across demographics. Results showed teachers agreed mass promotion causes learning gaps, poor preparedness, and reduced motivation, while existing remedial programs are insufficient. No significant perception differences were found across age, gender, service length, or designation, indicating shared concerns. The study concludes that automatic promotion and rigid curricula weaken learning and recommends a Math Mastery Support Program with diagnostic assessments, remediation, mastery-based progression, and enhanced classroom monitoring to improve proficiency and uphold academic standards.

Keywords: *mass promotion, mathematical proficiency, mastery-based learning, teacher perceptions, academic standards*

INTRODUCTION

Across many education systems, students advance through grade levels without fully mastering basic skills, creating a domino effect of widening learning gaps. This challenge is particularly evident in the Philippines, where mathematics education faces persistent deficiencies. The practice of mass promotion, in which students progress regardless of academic readiness, has become a critical concern in core subjects (UNESCO, 2022). Although intended to promote inclusivity, this practice has instead contributed to declining learning outcomes and has raised important questions about how to balance equity with academic standards.

Mathematical proficiency is a multifaceted construct encompassing conceptual understanding, procedural fluency, strategic competence, adaptive reasoning, and productive disposition (NCTM, 2025). Mastery of grade-level competencies builds a foundation for higher learning and essential problem-solving skills. Yet, Filipino students underperform; in the 2018 PISA, only 19% reached minimum mathematics proficiency, highlighting systemic weaknesses that hinder learning outcomes. EDCOM 2 (2023) further reports that 90.9% of 10-year-olds in the Philippines experience learning poverty—defined as the inability to read and understand simple texts—representing one of the highest rates worldwide. Because reading comprehension is fundamental to solving mathematical problems, weak literacy further worsens poor performance in mathematics (EDCOM 2, 2023; World Bank, 2022).

Mass promotion advances students without mastering grade-level competencies. In the Philippines, it stems partly from misinterpreting the U.S. “No Child Left Behind” policy. Although DepEd Order No. 8, s. 2015 sets a 75% passing requirement, automatic promotion is not mandated. Nevertheless, mass promotion has become deeply embedded in school culture and administrative practice. Studies in other developing countries likewise demonstrate that automatic promotion correlates with weaker reasoning abilities and lower academic achievement (Gaytos et al., 2019; Yeboah et al., 2020).

EDCOM 2 emphasizes addressing learning deficits, strengthening literacy and numeracy by Grade 3, and implementing 8–12 week recovery programs in secondary schools using diagnostic assessments. In one national high school, 40% of Grade 7 students were non-readers, yet teachers felt pressured to promote them, causing students to advance without mastery and requiring reteaching.

This study emphasizes the need to examine the link between promotion practices and mathematical proficiency to address the Philippine learning crisis. Understanding teachers' perspectives on automatic promotion can guide policy reforms ensuring skill mastery, especially amid DepEd's Matatag Curriculum and EDCOM 2 initiatives that risk failure if mass promotion persists.

Statement of the Problem

This study seeks to examine the relationship between high school mass promotion practices and mathematical proficiency among students, as perceived by math teachers. Specifically, it aims the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the mathematics teacher-respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age
 - 1.2 Sex
 - 1.3 Length of Service experience
 - 1.4 Designation
2. What are the perceptions of mathematics teachers regarding the relationship between high school promotion practices and students' mathematical proficiency in terms of:
 - 2.1 Promotion Practices
 - 2.2 Student Preparedness
 - 2.3 Resource Availability
 - 2.4 Impact on Motivation
 - 2.5 Academic Standards
3. Is there a significant relationship between high school promotion practices and mathematical proficiency based on their profiles?
4. Based on the findings of the study, what intervention program can be proposed to address the effects of promotion practices on students' mathematical proficiency?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This quantitative correlational study examines the relationship between high school promotion practices and students' mathematical proficiency, analyzing teachers' perceptions and profiles to determine how factors like mass promotion relate to mathematics performance without manipulating variables.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents are high school mathematics teachers directly involved in teaching, assessing, and promoting students, providing valuable insights on how promotion practices affect learners' mathematical proficiency through their firsthand experience and evaluation responsibilities.

Locale of the Study

The study will be conducted in public secondary schools in Abuyog, Leyte, Philippines, providing a representative setting to examine how mass promotion affects students' mathematical proficiency through authentic insights from mathematics teachers directly experiencing these practices.

Sample and Sampling Technique

This study uses census sampling, including all high school mathematics teachers from selected public schools in Abuyog, Leyte, to ensure accurate representation of promotion practices and their perceived effects on mathematical proficiency, enhancing the reliability and validity of the findings.

Research Instruments

The researcher will use a structured Likert-scale questionnaire to collect data on teachers' demographics and their perceptions of how promotion practices affect students' mathematical proficiency, including preparedness, resources, motivation, and academic standards.

Data Gathering Procedure

After securing the principal's approval, the researcher will distribute printed questionnaires to selected respondents in person, allowing one week for completion, with follow-up reminders sent to ensure maximum response and participation.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher will uphold ethical standards by securing voluntary participation, obtaining informed consent, and ensuring confidentiality. Completed questionnaires will be collected, anonymized, and handled carefully, with responses used solely for research purposes during encoding and analysis.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The researcher will use SPSS to analyze data, employing descriptive statistics for respondents' demographics and trends, and ANOVA to compare mean differences across promotion practices, preparedness, resources, motivation, and academic standards to identify significant variations.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This chapter presents the results, analysis and interpretation of data gathered from the answers to the questionnaires distributed to the field. The said data were presented in tabular form in accordance with the specific questions posited on statement of the problem.

1. What is the profile of the mathematics teacher-respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age
 - 1.2 Gender
 - 1.3 Length of Service
 - 1.4 Teacher's Designation

Table 1.1. Frequency and percentage Distribution of the Respondents in Terms of Age

AGE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
25-34	9	36%
35 – 44	5	20%
45 – 54	7	28%
55 – 65	4	16%
TOTAL	25	100%

Table 1.2. Frequency and percentage Distribution of the Respondents in Terms of Sex

SEX	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Male	8	32%
Female	17	68%
TOTAL	25	100%

Table 1.3. Frequency and percentage Distribution of the Respondents in Terms of Length of Service Experience

LENGTH OF SERVICE EXPERIENCE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
1 to 3	1	4%
4 to 6	2	8%
7 to 9	10	40%
10 to 14	6	24%
15+	6	24%
TOTAL	25	100%

Table 1.4. Frequency and percentage Distribution of the Respondents in Terms of Designation

DESIGNATION	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
TEACHER I	4	16%
TEACHER II	3	12%
TEACHER III	11	44%
MASTER TEACHER I	2	8%
MASTER TEACHER II	3	12%
MASTER TEACHER III	2	8%
TOTAL	25	100%

2. What are the perceptions of math teachers regarding the relationship between high school promotion practices and student's mathematical proficiency in terms of:

- 2.1 Promotion Practices
- 2.2 Student Preparedness
- 2.3 Resource Availability
- 2.4 Impact on Motivation
- 2.5 Academic Standards

Legend:

SCALE	RANGE	VERBAL INTERPRETATION
4	3.25-4.00	Strongly Agree
3	2.51-3.24	Agree
2	1.75-2.50	Disagree
1	1.00-1.74	Strongly Disagree

Table 2.1.

Promotion Practices	MEAN	VI
1. Students are promoted to the next grade level even without mastering mathematical competencies.	2.92	Agree
2. The promotion policy in our school occasionally allows students to move forward without meeting all math requirements.	2.76	Agree
3. I feel that current promotion practices may not always fully reflect students' mathematics performance.	3	Agree

4. Promotion to the next grade is often based on factors other than math achievement.	2.96	Agree
5. There are instances that I feel encouraged to support student promotion in math despite challenges in mastery.	2.52	Agree
6. The promotion process in my school may sometimes emphasize progression over complete mastery of math skills.	3	Agree
7. Promotion practices in our school weaken the importance of learning mathematics.	2.84	Agree
OVERALL WEIGHTED MEAN	2.86	Agree

Table 2.2.

Student Preparedness	MEAN	VI
1. Many students lack the necessary math background for their current grade.	3.44	Strongly Agree
2. Students struggle with new math topics due to insufficient prior knowledge.	3.44	Strongly Agree
3. It is common for promoted students to need additional support in foundational math skills.	3.2	Agree
4. Students often require extra help to catch up in math.	3.28	Strongly Agree
5. Students' lack of preparedness slows down the pace of math instruction.	3.28	Strongly Agree
6. I observe that some students have gaps in their understanding of basic math concepts.	3.48	Strongly Agree
7. Students who advance without fully mastering math may face challenges in higher grades.	3.44	Strongly Agree
OVERALL WEIGHTED MEAN	3.37	Strongly Agree

Table 2.3.

Resource Availability	MEAN	VI
1. Our school generally provides sufficient resources to support students who find math challenging.	2.60	Agree
2. There are enough remedial programs for students who need math support.	2.76	Agree
3. I have access to helpful materials that support students' improvement in math.	2.92	Agree
4. Our school offers interventions that are effective in supporting students with math difficulties.	2.56	Agree
5. There is enough time allocated for remedial math instruction.	2.48	Disagree
6. I receive support from administration to help struggling math students.	2.84	Agree
7. Students have access to tutoring or extra help in math.	2.64	Agree
OVERALL WEIGHTED MEAN	2.69	Agree

Table 2.4.

Impact on Motivation	MEAN	VI
1. Promotion practices may influence students' motivation to learn math.	2.76	Agree
2. Students are motivated to excel in math because their hard work directly impacts their promotion.	2.72	Agree
3. Students tend to be more motivated when promotion is linked to their math achievement.	2.60	Agree
4. Promotion policies can affect how accountable students feel for their math performance.	2.56	Agree
5. Students are more engaged in math when they see promotion as a reward for mastery.	2.84	Agree
6. Promotion practices affect students' attitudes towards math learning.	2.88	Agree
7. Students show greater confidence in their math activities when promotion criteria emphasize mastery.	2.64	Agree
OVERALL WEIGHTED MEAN	2.71	Agree

Table 2.5.

Academic Standards	MEAN	VI
1. Promotion practices in our school support maintaining strong academic standards in math.	2.68	Agree
2. Our school generally enforces clear math requirements for student promotion.	2.92	Agree
3. Our promotion policies maintain high academic standards.	2.88	Agree
4. Promotion decisions are aligned with the math curriculum standards.	2.88	Agree
5. Promotion practices can influence the level of rigor in math instruction.	2.88	Agree
6. The school regularly reviews and updates standards related to math instruction.	2.76	Agree
7. Students are encouraged to meet high expectations in math before being promoted criteria emphasize mastery.	2.48	Disagree
OVERALL WEIGHTED MEAN	2.78	Agree

2. Is there a significant relationship between high school promotion practices and mathematical proficiency based on their profiles?

Table 3.1. Significant relationship between High School Promotion Practices and Students' Mathematical Proficiency according to Age

VARIABLES	F-VALUE	SIG	DECISION	INTERPRETATION
Promotion Practices	.072	.974	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Student Preparedness	1.519	.239	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Resource Availability	.820	.497	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Impact on Motivation	.216	.884	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Academic Standards	.094	.962	Accept H_0	Not Significant

Table 3.2. Significant relationship between high school promotion practices and mathematical proficiency according to Sex

VARIABLES	F-VALUE	SIG	DECISION	INTERPRETATION
Promotion Practices	.222	.642	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Student Preparedness	.073	.790	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Resource Availability	.060	.938	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Impact on Motivation	.271	.608	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Academic Standards	.183	.673	Accept H_0	Not Significant

Table 3.3. Significant relationship between high school promotion practices and students' mathematical proficiency according to Length of Service Experience

VARIABLES	F-VALUE	SIG	DECISION	INTERPRETATION
Promotion Practices	.976	.443	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Student Preparedness	1.228	.331	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Resource Availability	.618	.655	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Impact on Motivation	1.459	.252	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Academic Standards	1.209	.338	Accept H_0	Not Significant

Table 3.4. Significant relationship between high school promotion practices and mathematical proficiency according to Designation

VARIABLES	F-VALUE	SIG	DECISION	INTERPRETATION
Promotion Practices	1.246	.327	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Student Preparedness	1.192	.350	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Resource Availability	1.742	.173	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Impact on Motivation	1.372	.278	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Academic Standards	1.040	.423	Accept H_0	Not Significant

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter presents the summary of findings, so conclusions drawn from the findings and the corresponding recommendations.

This study was taken with the general objective of examining the relationship between high school mass promotion practices and mathematical proficiency among high school students, as perceived by public math teachers of Abuyog, Leyte.

Summary of Findings

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the mathematics teacher-respondents in terms of:
- 2.

1.1 Age

Most of the mathematics teacher-respondents are 25–34 years old (36%), followed by 45–54 years old (28%), while the smallest group belongs to the 55–65 age bracket (16%).

1.2 Gender

Most of the participants are female, making up 68%, whereas male represent only 32%, highlighting the female dominance in the teaching field.

1.3 Length of Service experience

Most respondents have 7–9 years' teaching experience (40%), nearly half (48%) over 10 years, while only 12% are beginners with 1–6 years, indicating overall experience.

1.4 Designation

Among respondents, 44% are Teacher III, 16% Teacher I, 12% Teacher II, and 28% Master Teachers, indicating most are regular classroom teachers in lower to mid-level positions, with fewer occupying higher or advanced teaching roles.

3. What are the perceptions of math teachers regarding the relationship between high school promotion practices and students' mathematical proficiency in terms of:

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National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

2.1 Promotion Practices

With an overall mean of 2.86, findings reveal that teachers believe promotion practices often advance students without mastering math skills, driven by policies prioritizing progression over genuine learning.

2.2 Student Preparedness

With an overall mean of 3.37, teachers strongly agree that mass promotion leaves students unprepared, creating learning gaps and slowing progress due to weak foundational math skills.

2.3 Resource Availability

With an overall mean of 2.69, teachers agree that schools provide adequate math resources and support, though limited time for remedial instruction (2.48) indicates insufficient help for struggling learners.

2.4 Impact on Motivation

With an overall mean of 2.71, teachers agree that promotion practices influence students' motivation in math; however, 2.56 highlights weak accountability effects among students.

2.5 Academic Standards

Teachers agree (2.78) that promotion practices align with academic standards, but a lower score (2.48) shows true mastery before promotion is inconsistently emphasized.

3. Is there a significant relationship between high school promotion practices and mathematical proficiency based on teachers' profiles?

Findings show no significant relationship between promotion practices and students' mathematical proficiency across teacher profiles, with all p-values above 0.05, indicating consistent perceptions on promotion, preparedness, resources, motivation, and standards.

4. Based on the findings of the study, what intervention program can be proposed to address the effects of promotion practices on students' mathematical proficiency?

The study proposes the Math Mastery Support Program in five Abuyog high schools, using diagnostic tests, remediation, tutoring, peer instruction, and policy monitoring to enhance mastery, close learning gaps, and strengthen mathematical proficiency.

Conclusions

The study found that teachers' views on promotion practices and their impact on students' math skills were consistent across age, gender, service length, and position. Teachers agreed mass promotion is a serious issue, creating learning gaps and poor preparedness, while mastery-based promotion enhances motivation, discipline, and mathematical understanding.

The scripted curriculum further limits teachers' flexibility, and combined with mass promotion, results in shallow learning and weak foundations, leaving students unprepared for advanced concepts and real-life problem-solving.

School pressures to maintain high promotion and completion rates often lead to advancing students despite low performance, and teachers may hesitate to retain them to avoid additional workload. However, ensuring mastery before promotion is crucial; retention should be applied when necessary to safeguard learning integrity.

In conclusion, mass promotion and rigid curricula weaken academic standards and student competence. Schools should implement mastery-based promotion, strengthen remediation, and

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Volume V, Issue XI (November 2025), pp.51-62, International
ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X
Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com
Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services
DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183
National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

empower teachers with resources and flexibility. Collaborative efforts among educators, leaders, and students are essential to close learning gaps and build strong mathematical foundations.

Recommendations

Based on the study's findings, it is recommended that the Department of Education adopt mastery-based promotion with diagnostic assessments and clear competency standards. School administrators should implement the Math Mastery Support Program with sufficient time, staff, and resources for remediation and effective teaching. Mathematics teachers must address learning gaps early, use formative assessments, and adapt instruction to student needs. Students should take responsibility for their learning, prioritizing mastery over automatic promotion. Future researchers are encouraged to study the long-term effects of mastery-based promotion, its implementation across contexts, and the roles of parents, technology, and teacher training in supporting student proficiency.

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DOI 10.5281/zenodo.17586754

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